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Microwave Remote Sensing Properties of Soil in India

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Abstract :

In this paper an attempt has been made to analyze microwave remote sensing dielectric behaviour of soil in India. A researcher may research any part of the world but it has been seen from literature review more or less 15-20 states are in well position to recognize in the field of microwave remote sensing dielectric behaviour viz : Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan, J & K, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Kerala, Gujarat, West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Haryana, Maharashtra, Punjab. A different study predicts that the dielectric properties of soil at microwave frequencies are the function of its physico-chemical constituents. The Physical capacities of a soil are influenced by the size, proportion, arrangement and composition of the soil particles. Microwave remote, sensing techniques are now a day's widely adopted and used to estimate the presence of natural resources underneath the ground surface. The present study has been taken to have an idea of microwave remote sensing

characteristics of soil properties in agriculture for food purpose. These dielectric properties can be used to predict the soil fertility and health. In this paper it has been also discussed about microwave remote sensing characteristics of soil for agriculture. The quality of soil is controlled by physical, chemical and biological components of soil and their interactions. The soil has physical, chemical as well as electrical properties, colour, texture, grain size, bulk density etc. comprise the physical properties, nutrients, organic matter, pH, etc. comprise chemical properties while, electrical properties include dielectric constant, electrical conductivity and permeability. The concept of soil health and soil quality has consistently evolved with an increase in the understanding of soils and soil quality attributes. The dielectric constant of soil is dependent on the bulk density of soil and hence porosity and wilting point of soil. The dielectric constant of Indian soils is dependent on the texture of soil i.e. the percent content of sand, silt and clay.

Keywords : Microwave, Remote Sensing, Soil Quality, fertility, dielectric, dielectric constant, nutrients, texture.

Introduction :

A soil is generally characterized by the size of its particles. It is known that more than eighteen essential elements are present in the soil. i.e. Molybdenum (MoO_4^{2-}) and nickel (Ni^{+2}), zinc (Zn^{2+}), copper (Cu^{2+}), chlorine (Cl^-), cobalt (Co^{2+}), hydrogen (H_2O), oxygen (O_2 , H_2O), (Ni^{2+}), nitrogen (NO_3^+ , NH_4^+), phosphorus ($H_2PO_4^-$, HPO_4^{2-}), potassium (K^+), calcium (Ca_2^+), magnesium (Mg_2^+), sulfur (SO_4^{2-}), iron (Fe^{2+}), manganese (Mn^{2+}), boron (HBO_3), carbon (CO_2), further it has been noted that eighteen elements considered essential to plant as well as soil growth.

Soil shows physical properties, chemical properties and geographical properties. Moisture content is the nucleus of all parameter. Use of soil moisture as an input produces slightly better results compared to that using brightness temperature. The physical linkages between soil moisture and soil texture is much stronger than those between brightness temperature and soil texture. At a particular point in time and place soil moisture and dielectric behaviour is influenced by precipitation history, texture and heterogeneity of the soil, which is key to water holding capacity, topography, the slope and variation of land surface, which affects runoff and infiltration and the vegetation and land cover, which influences deep percolation.

Study of microwave remote sensing dielectric behaviour of soil gives an outcome about soil fertility and production. The technique of remote sensing enhances the analytical study. Remote sensing is defined as an art and the science which deals with obtaining information about objects on earth surface by analysis of data, received from a remote platform.

Remote sensing is the backbone of the space programme. Remote sensing plays a prominent role in many domains related to the observation of the earth such as agriculture monitoring, military battles, and cover, oceanography, etc. Remote sensing is often defined as acquiring information about objects without being in direct physical contact with them. Our ears, eyes, and cameras are examples of remote sensors. More specifically, remote sensing is the science of collecting and interpreting electromagnetic information about the earth using sensors on platforms in our atmosphere (balloons, airplanes) or in space (satellites).

The electromagnetic (EM) spectrum describes a continuous spectrum of energy. This energy is caused by the movement of electrical charges. Visible light, or the light that our eyes can detect, is just a small portion of the EM spectrum. Using specialized sensors, we can look into the realm of the invisible and see a greater portion of the EM spectrum than is possible with the human eye. Electromagnetic radiation is the source of all signals collected by remote sensing instruments. The region of the EM spectrum that is measured depends on the sensor's characteristics. Sensors collect data by separating reflected portions of the EM spectrum into separate bands as shown in the figure below. Note that the image produced using one band is black and white; this is often called a "gray-scale image".

Microwaves contribute very insignificantly to the energy budget of the earth atmosphere system. Microwaves mode of travel and interaction, with the atmospheric environment and at the earth surface, in this remote frequency range renders, it a valuable tool to obtain information about dielectric properties and soil moisture. It is important parameters for the earth atmosphere energy budget and its hydrological cycle.

Materials and Methods & Theoretical Consideration :

The infinite sample method described by Altshuler is used for the Measurement of dielectric properties, besides this the instrument AAS has been utilized. Sweats are grouped into different classes based on mass ratio of soil separates namely sand, silt and clay which are called Soil textural classes. Soil textural classification is given below :

Broad Groups	Textural Classes	Important Characteristics
Coarse textured soils Sandy soils	Sand loamy sand	Feel gritty, low specific surface area, low electrical activity, non-sticky and non plastic in nature, high drainage and aeration, low water and nutrients retention, generally low productivity.
Medium - Textured soils (Loamy soils)	Sandy loam, loam, silt loam, silt, sandy clay loam, clay loam, silty clay loam	Feel smooth, cohesive, good drainage, medium water and nutrients retention capacity, low plasticity, low stikness, easy to till, productive soil, properties vary with the dominant soil fraction, the content.
Fine - textured soils Clayey - soils	Sand clay Silt clay Clay	Feel sticky, very large specific surface area, theoretically active, have high CEC, high water and nutrients retention, high total porosity, poor drainage, difficult to till, productive soils.

The dielectric properties of soil called from different regions of CVRU campus and Kulgaon district has been a study at AAS. Due to COVID-19 the measurement of dielectric constant at X band frequency has not been performed for farmed but likely to be performed in the future. The following relation has been used as :

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$$

$$\epsilon^* = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_g}\right)^2} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda_g}{\lambda_c}\right)^2} \left[\frac{r - j \tan k (D - D_R)}{1 - j \tan k (D - D_R)} \right]^2$$

Where, λ_c , λ_g and K cutoff wave length, guide wave length and wave vector, r is voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) and D and D_R are the position of first minima with and without sample respectively.

The gravimetric soil moisture content in percentage $W_c(\%)$ is calculated using wet (W_1) and dry (W_2) soil masses using the following relation :

$$W_c(\%) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2} \times 100$$

From the measurement of dielectric constant and dielectric loss other electrical parameters can be obtained.

$$\sigma = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon''$$

And

$$\tau = \frac{\epsilon''}{\omega \epsilon'}$$

Soil Sampling :

Soil samples are taken from different locations of district Bilaspur and Mungeli. For each sample 15 mm topsoil was removed and 3 pits were dug. A composite sample of about 1 to 2kg represents one site. Same procedure is followed for all the samples collected from the study area. Soil samples were collected from 30 different location of Bilaspur and Mungeli in a zigzag pattern. Representing soil samples were collected with wooden tools to avoid any contamination of the soils. 4 to 5 pits were dug for each sample. From each pit sample were collected at a depth of 0-20 cm.

Dielectric constant plays pivotal role in the farming. All soil parameters are affected by dielectric constant so it is very alarming for the production of food grains. In our country Common life is based on mainly on agriculture. So in this contest concerned scientists, pioneers, researchers are performing landmark research to fulfill needs of country. Moreover, fifteen or sixteen states are involved in such type of research. Some of the researchers are -

- From Kerala, Dr. Mohan, Dr. S. Mridul, Dr. P. Mohanan and Dr. Binu Paul.
- From Maharastra, V.V. Navarkhele, Dr. H.C. Choudhary, Dr. V.J. Sinde, Dr. D.V. Ahire, Dr. A.K. Kapre.
- In Madhya Pradesh, Dr. J.P. Shukla works is very remarkable.

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- Dr. T. Panda, B.B. Kar and Dr. M.C. Borah from Assam.
- From Chhattisgarh, Dr. S.K. Patel, Dr. S.K. Shrivastava, Dr. Samir Bajpai, and Dr. U.K. Dewangan.
- Dr. Manab Chkravarty, P.R. Choudhary, Dr. V.K. Shrivastava and Gadani research in this field from Gujarat.
- From Jammu & Kashmir, Dr. Haseem-Hasan, Hazarathbal and, Dr. H.S. Bali works in this field.
- In Karnataka important research done by, Dr. Chetan-Bohra and Vivek-Ranjan.
- Dr. S.N. Jha, Rajeev Sharma, (CIPHET), from Ludhiana Punjab.
- From IIT Roorkee Uttarakhand, Dr. D. Singh done works in this field.
- Sudip Saran (CEERI), V.K. Gupta, O.P.N. Calla, Anil Kumar, R.A. Jangid, and Vivek Yadav from Rajasthan.
- From Uttar Pradesh Devendra Singh and Jitendra Behari works is very important.
- Dr. P.K. Paul and R. Mishra research is remarkable in field of remote sensing.

Data of Sampling & Observation :

The five samples were collected from five places. The details are as follows :

S1 : Chorbhatti (J)

S2 : Baghamudda

S3 : Sangwakapa

S4 : Chorbhatti

S5 : Birgaon

Observation – 1

Parameters / Samples	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
pH	7.6	8.0	6.3	5.1	5.1
EC (ds/m)	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.4
OC (%)	0.45	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.15
N (kg/hact.)	250	238	225	263	275
P (kg/hact.)	18.81	11.64	13.44	11.64	15.23
K (kg/hact.)	331	470	268	313	380
S (ppm)	12.50	10.00	12.50	11.25	11.25
Zn (ppm)	0.919	1.213	0.912	0.712	2.212
B (ppm)	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0
Fe (ppm)	21.22	12.15	21.11	12.30	11.23
Mn (ppm)	13.40	10.12	17.30	16.25	25.13
Cu (ppm)	1.121	1.121	0.930	0.712	0.912
Sand (%)	11.17	10.95	12.32	12.01	10.23
Silt (%)	64.40	56.00	58.63	57.23	56.32
Clay (%)	20.00	12.32	9.32	11.32	14.32

Observation – 2

Parameters / Samples	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
pH	6.70	6.80	6.70	7.10	6.90	7.20
EC (ds/m)	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.40	0.40
OC (%)	0.15	0.30	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.30
N (kg/hact.)	301	363	313	313	275	301
P (kg/hact.)	16.18	18.82	21.50	16.12	17.02	17.02
K (kg/hact.)	481	439	448	459	470	481
S (ppm)	23.75	28.75	32.76	31.25	31.25	12.50
Zn (ppm)	0.64	0.41	0.71	0.83	1.12	0.92
B (ppm)	6.00	6.00	4.00	6.00	7.00	6.00
Fe (ppm)	8.31	17.31	9.12	10.11	9.18	31.91
Mn (ppm)	30.12	34.13	47.14	12.42	30.14	10.14
Cu (ppm)	1.89	1.95	1.19	0.69	0.64	1.32
Sand (%)	12.15	10.23	9.56	11.45	10.96	11.52
Silt (%)	62.01	59.29	65.13	63.25	65.12	66.32
Clay (%)	21.01	19.96	20.32	20.11	21.14	20.96

Result and Discussion :

Soil texture has remarkable effect on the dielectric constant. A soil is made up of four elements : inorganic or mineral fraction (derived from the parent material), organic material, air, and water. From an observation of a real soil profile one can identify colour, texture, structure, and other properties of soil.

Fig. : Variation of real part of dielectric constant with % of Moisture Content in Soil.

Fig. : Variation of dielectric constant with % of sand in Soil.

Fig. : Variation of dielectric constant with % of silt in Soil.

Fig. : Variation of dielectric constant with % of clay in Soil.

Fig. : Variation of dielectric constant with moisture content % for black soil.

Fig. : Variation of EC with dielectric constant of black soil.

Fig. : Variation of EC with texture of sand.

Fig. : Variation of EC with texture of silt.

Fig. : Variation of EC with texture of clay.

Fig. : Variation of EC with texture of sand.

Fig. : Variation of DC with texture of silt.

Fig. : Variation of EC with porosity % of black soil.

Fig. : Percentage of clay within soil at various places/state of India.

Fig. : Percentage of sand in soil at various state/place in India.

Fig. : Percentage of sand in soil at various state/place in India.

S/N	Sample	Dry Soil	10%	20%	30%	40%
1.	Mungeli (B1)	3.09	7.11	9.73	13.98	18.41
2.	Bilaspur (B2)	3.11	7.21	10.22	14.02	18.98
3.	Janjgir-Champa (B3)	3.16	7.41	10.38	15.35	19.32
4.	Raigarh (B4)	3.19	7.53	10.68	15.65	19.62
5.	Korba (B5)	3.25	7.69	11.02	16.06	20.01
6.	Koriya (S1)	3.07	6.98	9.12	13.10	18.21
7.	Ambikapur (S2)	3.08	7.14	10.01	13.94	18.72
8.	Balrampur (S3)	3.11	7.30	10.23	15.20	19.23
9.	Surajpur (S4)	3.14	7.42	10.54	15.41	19.48
10.	Jashpur (S5)	3.17	7.59	10.99	15.63	19.72

Table : Dielectric constant of Bilaspur and Sarguja zone.

Fig. : Dielectric characteristics of soil in Bilaspur zone.

Fig. : Dielectric characteristics of soil in Sarguja zone.

Fig. : Percentage of silt within soil at various places/state of India.

Fig. : Percentage of sand in soil at various state / place in India.

Fig. : Percentage of sand, silt and clay within soil in various places/states of India.

Fig. : Percentage of "ε-1" within soil in various places/states of India.

Fig. : Percentage of organic carbon in Indian soil from different parts of country.

Fig. : Percentage of organic carbon in Indian soil from different parts of country.

Fig. : Percentage of pH in Indian soil from different parts of country.

Fig. : Texture of soil in various places of India.

Fig. : Bulk density (mgm⁻³) in soil in various places of India.

Fig. : Percent of various soils in India.

Fig. : Parameter of different types of soil for different samples.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions have been given below :

- Electric conductivity slowly increases with dielectric constant.
- Increasing the percentage of sand, Electrical conductivity decreases.
- Increasing the percentage of silt, Electrical conductivity increases.
- Increasing the percentage of silt, Electrical conductivity sharply increases.
- Increasing the percentage of clay, dielectric constant increases.
- Increasing the porosity, Electrical conductivity increases.
- Increasing the bulk density, Electrical conductivity decreases.
- Increasing the porosity, dielectric constant randomly increases.
- Increasing the bulk density, dielectric constant decreases.

- Increasing the pH, the value of Electrical conductivity decreases.
- Increasing the value of pH, dielectric constant decreases, but at the pH value of 7 the dielectric constant is high.
- Increasing the value of nitrogen electrical conductivity shortly increases.
- Increasing the value of phosphorous the electrical conductivity increase.
- Increasing the value of potassium, the value of electrical conductivity increase.
- Increasing the value of calcium, the value of electrical conductivity gradually increases.
- Where as in the black soil increasing the value of nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium, calcium, and magnesium, the dielectric constant gradually increase.

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